

RADx-UP PROGRAM EVALUATION

Project Implementation Survey: Baseline Results

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Executive Summary

Purpose and Overview of Methods

The purpose of this report is to describe the qualitative and quantitative findings from the baseline RADx-UP Project Implementation Survey.

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team developed and deployed a RADx-UP Project Implementation Survey to RADx-UP projects to better understand how they carry out their objectives and activities related to:

- COVID-19 testing and vaccination implementation activities, successes, and challenges.
- Partnerships & community engagement activities, successes, and challenges
- Data collection, analysis & dissemination
- Broader project outcomes, impacts, and sustainability.

T&E deployed the baseline survey to 138 projects (including supplemental grant awardees) from Spring 2022 to Spring 2023 and collected data from 83 (61% response rate).

Projects Implementation Successes

COVID-19 Testing and/or Vaccination.

- **Resources and Promotional Strategies:** Projects most frequently utilized a variety of community-based outreach strategies such as health communication messaging (n=36/83; 43%), providing testing locations (n=25/83; 30%), employing community health workers (CHW) (n=24/83; 29%) and using social media (n=20/83; 24%) to improve testing and vaccination uptake. In-depth responses from twelve projects highlighted successful community outreach using social media, text messages, and project websites, effectively recruiting participants and promoting COVID-19 awareness.
- **Culturally Tailored Approaches:** Projects (n=28/83; 34%) successfully increased COVID-19 testing uptake by employing culturally responsive strategies, such as hiring staff from the community, providing translation services, and crafting culturally appropriate messaging.
- **Testing Accessibility and Procurement:** Most projects (n=39/47; 83%) indicated success in increasing testing accessibility, with many able to connect with the CDCC for support, highlighting the CDCC's responsiveness in addressing challenges. More than half of projects (n=10/15; 66.6%) indicated that the CDCC has been responsive to their requests around procurement assistance, while 40% (n=6/15) of projects agreed that the CDCC helped them resolve their procurement challenges.

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Partnerships and Community Engagement

- **Effective Multi-level Partnerships:** Over half (n=52/80; 65%) of the projects collaborated with community-based organizations, forming partnerships to overcome implementation barriers, address recruitment challenges, and build trust within target communities.
- **Active Community Engagement:** The active involvement of community advisory boards (n=38/83; 46%) and steering committees (n=5/83; 6%) played a crucial role in providing guidance on testing

strategies, tailoring interventions, and facilitating bi-directional learning between academic and community partners.

- **Building Community Capacity:** Community-based partners (n=48/51; 94% of projects) actively contributed to project planning and implementation, engaging in outreach, recruitment, retention, study design, data collection, and utilizing findings to enhance implementation quality. Projects focused on building community capacity through trust-building, ensuring community-based partners took leadership roles, and providing training opportunities to develop research skills (n=77, n=46, n=28 projects, respectively).
- **Cultural Responsiveness:** Projects demonstrated cultural responsiveness by employing diverse staff (n=49/83; 59%), acknowledging historical trauma (n=41/83; 49.4%), providing training in culturally responsive care (n=37/83; 44.6%), and using plain language in research products (n=35/83; 42%).
- **Addressing SDOH needs:** Beyond COVID-19 interventions, project partnership collaborations (n=2) addressed broader social needs, such as cash assistance, food distribution, and connecting participants to primary care services, highlighting the lasting impact of community partnerships beyond the pandemic.

Projects' Impacts and Sustainability

Figure 1: RADx-UP Projects Impacts and Sustainability

- **Community Capacity Building for Research:** Many projects plan to sustain community engagement strategies and activities after grant funding ends, indicating a commitment to sustaining community-engaged research.

- **Community and Public Health benefits:** Projects contributed to public health infrastructure by providing testing in underserved communities, particularly valuable during times of strained public health resources. Survey results suggest that many projects plan to continue their community engagement strategies after grant funding ends, indicating a commitment to sustaining efforts to improve access to health and social services.
- **Economic and Policy Benefits:** Projects successfully reduced the cost of testing through various means, including reducing the monetary costs of tests and accelerating test processes. Over half (56%) of the projects provided economic benefits, primarily through minimizing test costs (n=38/83; 46%), time to complete tests (n=33/83; 40%), and time to receive test results (n=28/83; 34%). Some projects (n=23/82; 28%) engaged in policy activities, such as presenting data to government agencies, contributing to policy briefs, and participating in advisory committees, demonstrating a broader impact beyond testing.
- **Pandemic Preparedness:** Survey results suggest that many project activities (n=59/82; 72%), especially COVID-19 testing (n=43/47; 91%), are agile and replicable, contributing to improved pandemic preparedness in underserved communities.

Projects Implementation Challenges

Figure 2: RADx-UP Projects Implementation Challenges

- **Partnership Coordination and Community Capacity:** Five (5) projects faced difficulties in coordinating and engaging diverse stakeholders, securing support from partners, overcoming data-sharing roadblocks, and addressing resource constraints. Six projects encountered capacity limitations, particularly in engaging partners and community-based organizations.
- **Community-Specific Barriers:** Six (6) projects encountered unique challenges related to study settings and target populations. For example, coordinating with Pacific Islander communities or migrant workers engaged in hourly work was challenging due to time limitations. Migrant workers also hesitated to discuss COVID-19 testing or vaccination due to concerns about being absent from work (when tested positive for COVID-19). Finally, despite translation efforts, language barriers affected questionnaire completion time.
- **Data-Related:** Thirty-two (32) projects described facing challenges in data collection, analysis, and dissemination due to the rapid evolution of the pandemic, COVID-19 fatigue, staffing shortages, and

lack of data science expertise. Also, Difficulties were encountered in administering surveys and dealing with data transfer, harmonization, and management delays. Also, projects required assistance in translating findings into user-focused products for community dissemination and timely publication in reputable journals.

- **Other External Environmental Factors:** Projects' testing activities (n=11 projects) were impacted by environmental factors beyond their control. They observed COVID-19 and testing fatigue among their populations due to declining interest in the pandemic, decreasing infection rates, and the perceived reduced value of testing due to widespread vaccination availability.

Conclusion

- The RADx-UP projects have successfully implemented COVID-19 testing and vaccination interventions, leading to increased testing accessibility, community capacity-building, and public health preparedness. However, the dissemination and uptake of testing strategies in practice is challenging due to factors such as COVID-19 fatigue and reduced perception of severity.
- Although RADx-UP Projects contributed significantly to developing community-led research collaboratives, we still need to understand the longer-term impact of community engagement strategies on improving health equity outcomes and explore ways to maintain community participation in testing and vaccination programs as public perceptions evolve.

Overview

The National Institutes of Health (NIH)-supported Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program funds projects across the US, its territories, and Tribal Nations to address COVID-19 testing disparities. RADx-UP projects (herein referred to as projects) use various community engagement (CE) models, frameworks, and principles to increase COVID-19 testing and vaccination access and pandemic preparedness among underserved communities.

Evaluation Objectives and Report

The Tracking and Evaluation Team (T&E) at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (UNC) oversees the comprehensive mixed-methods evaluation of RADx-UP. The overarching evaluation questions are:

COVID-19 Testing Determinants, Outcomes, Impacts, and Learning

- To what extent have the RADx-UP projects achieved their aims, goals, outcomes, and sustained impacts?
- What are the associations between social, ethical, and behavioral factors and COVID-19 testing?

Community Engagement and Community-Academic Partnerships

- What was the extent of projects' community engagement activities and community-academic partnerships in RADx-UP?
- How did these activities and partnerships influence projects' ability to achieve outcomes and sustained impacts?

Community Health and Equity

- What general conclusions can be drawn about improving community health, through increased access to COVID-19 testing, and health equity through a RADx-UP CDCC program approach?

As part of the evaluation, T&E developed a RADx-UP Project Implementation Survey, to assess projects' process, outcomes, and impacts over time. Specifically, this survey was designed to better understand how projects carry out their objectives and activities related to 1. COVID-19 testing and research; 2. Partnerships & community engagement; and 3. Data collection, analysis & dissemination. Additionally, we sought to understand how projects carried out their activities with consideration of diversity, equity & inclusion (DEI), attention to language & communication access to reach priority populations, and use of Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) support. Lastly, we sought to understand project impacts (including community capacity-building for research, policy and economic benefits, and community and public health impacts) and how those impacts may be sustained after project close out.

This report presents baseline survey findings that can help the CDCC communicate and replicate projects' implementation successes, address and mitigate challenges for active projects, and synthesize lessons learned to support legacy planning.

Methods

Survey Development

In Spring 2022, T&E developed the RADx-UP Project Implementation Survey for baseline data collection of projects' activities with multiple CDCC leaders and staff stakeholders' feedback to ensure face validity, prevent duplication of data collection within the data collection ecosystem, and reduce participant cognitive burden. The baseline survey consisted of seven sections: 1: Project Resources, 2: Project Services, 3: Partnerships and Community Engagement, 4: Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion, 5: Language and Communication Access, 6: Data Collection, Analysis, and Dissemination, 7: Project Impact and Sustainability. The project implementation survey captures quantitative and qualitative data and contains a variety of items and types of responses (including categorical, Likert-type scale, and open-ended).

Guiding Frameworks.

The seven survey sections and corresponding items were developed based upon selected evaluation indicators from the conceptual frameworks and models that undergird the RADx-UP Program Evaluation including: 1. Reach, Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation, and Maintenance (RE-AIM)¹; 2. Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM)²; 3. Social Ecological Model (SEM)³; and 4. Culturally Effective Organizations Framework⁴.

FIGURE 3. The RE-AIM, SEM, and TSBM Evaluation Frameworks and Their Components

The table in [Appendix A](#) describes the information collected in each survey section.

In Fall 2022, the baseline survey was revised to capture more specific information on the methods and approaches used by projects implementing and researching behavioral health interventions for testing. These items were developed based on the Behavior Change Technique Taxonomy (BCTT)⁵. T&E will conduct

a separate analysis of and report findings on the BCTT data.

Survey Administration

From Spring 2022 to Spring 2023, T&E recruited projects to participate in the survey and deployed it to project representatives.

Recruitment. T&E recruited projects individually to participate in the survey during monthly meetings coordinated by the Engagement Impact Team (EIT) or through tailored emails that described the survey. The recruitment process identified a deployment date and project representative to participate. We selected our approach to support our intensive initial recruitment strategy, which was designed to attain a high response rate and in recognition of the different project life cycles.

Sample. T&E deployed the baseline survey to 138 projects (including supplemental grant awardees) and collected data from 84 (61% response rate). We excluded 13 active projects from survey data collection because they either experienced grant administrative challenges or were sampled to participate in RADx-UP Project Implementation interviews. The interviews provided more contextual information on project implementation from both academic and community partners and findings have been reported previously⁶.

Data Analysis

We descriptively analyzed quantitative items to capture and illustrate projects' implementation trends. We thematically analyzed qualitative open-ended items using both inductive and deductive coding to understand the broad conceptual ideas expressed across projects' responses. **Appendix B** lists the thematic codes and frequency of codes for project responses.

Project Characteristics

In addition to our mixed methods analysis of project responses to survey items, we also descriptively analyzed the project characteristics of survey respondents which include: 1. RADx-UP priority population(s) served; and 2. Project geographic location. The analysis shows that projects reached diverse underserved populations and implemented their activities across diverse geographic regions (**Figures 4 and 5**).

Underserved populations served by RADx-UP projects (n=120)

* 7 projects are missing information on target population served, see Appendix C for "other" categories

Figure 4. Underserved Population Served by RADx-UP Projects.

RADx-UP Projects Count by U.S. Region (n = 121)

Figure 5. RADx-UP Projects Counts Across the US Region.

Results

Survey Respondents.

Most of the survey respondents as shown in **Figure 6** were project managers (n=45/83; 54%) or principal investigators (PIs) (n=36/83; 43%), and the remaining respondents were other administrative or operational staff (n=8/83; 10%)

Figure 6. Role Of Participants within the RADx-UP Projects

COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination Uptake.

More than half of projects (n=47/82; 57.5%) reported distributing COVID-19 tests which includes on-site testing and/or self-testing kits for projects that reported that they distributed tests (n=47/82; 57%), the average number of tests expected to be administered monthly was 507. Most (83%) of the 47 testing projects indicated agreement or strong agreement that their project is successful in increasing testing accessibility among their priority population(s).

Implementation Successes: Strategies to Improve COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination Uptake

Developing and Disseminating Community-Based Outreach and Education Resources to Improve COVID-19 Vaccination and Testing.

Projects indicated that they used multiple strategies to improve testing in their priority population(s) as depicted in **Figure 7**. The most frequently reported strategies were health communication, education, and/or messaging strategies (n=36/83; 43.4%); testing locations (n=25/83; 30%); Community Health Workers/volunteers (24/83; 29%); social media (n=20/83; 24%); and testing workflows (n=18/83; 21.7%). Less frequently reported strategies were testing technology (n=14/83; 17%); other approaches (n=14/83; 17%); technical assistance (n=12/83; 14.5%); facilitation and learning collaboratives (n=12/83; 14.5%); contact tracing (n=6/83; 7%) telemedicine/telehealth (n=6/83; 7%); or risk assessment tools (n=4/83; 5%).

Figure 7. Strategies RADx-UP Projects use to Improve COVID-19 Testing Reach

Twelve projects gave more in-depth responses on how they developed community outreach and education resources to spur intervention uptake. They reported employing social media, text messages (n=5/12 projects) and project websites (n=4/12 projects) to recruit participants, promote COVID-19 awareness and reach testing targets. Also, projects promoted COVID-19 testing and vaccination knowledge (n=4/12 projects) through community forums, utilizing interactive web-based data dissemination approaches and worked with community health workers to promote awareness.

"Participants have received weekly text messages for 12 weeks with different COVID related messages and a link that

directs them to additional information on our project website. Participants have engaged with the website by voting like or dislike on each message and also leaving comments to share additional thoughts on each topic. The intervention group has also completed 2 educational sessions led by a lay health worker to learn about the COVID-19 pandemic, testing, and vaccination.”

Increasing COVID-19 Testing Uptake through Culturally Responsive and Tailored Implementation Strategies

Most projects successfully increased COVID-19 testing uptake in their project communities through utilizing culturally responsive and tailored intervention strategies, including leveraging their community partnerships to deliver intervention.

Approximately 28 out of 83 projects gave in-depth responses on how increased testing uptake using culturally responsive and tailored intervention strategies. They used culturally responsive strategies (n= 14 projects) such as hiring staff directly from the community, providing translation services (n=6 projects), crafting culturally appropriate messaging (n=9 projects) to motivate testing and delivering interventions congruent with community needs and values. Projects also reported they experienced increased COVID-19 testing uptake by tailoring testing intervention strategies to their community needs (n= 10 projects) by meeting respondents where they are, providing at-home or school-based testing (n= 6 projects), providing tests at multiple location (n= 3 projects) and providing transportation or other financial incentives to motivate people.

“We successfully implemented two community-based [with our community partners], mass “test and response” campaigns in 2021. Through these campaigns and post-campaign outreach, we tested 1,481 people for COVID-19 in two low-income, majority-Latinx communities. In 2022 we launched new community-responsive COVID-19 testing activities including drop-in and “as needed” testing at our community-based sites performed by [our local community health volunteers], surveillance testing for local businesses, and decentralized distribution of over the counter (OTC) test kits. Through these activities, we have performed 6,380 tests and have distributed 1,232 OTC kits.”

Projects’ efforts in tailoring implementation services to fit the needs and cultural norms of their target population [**Figure 8**].

- **Accessibility.** Most projects (89.8%) agreed that all services are provided in the priority populations’ preferred language or communication mode.
- **Accommodation.** Many projects (92.4%) agreed that their project staff knew how to accommodate the language and communication needs of diverse members of their priority population(s) to improve access to project services.

Figure 8: RADx-UP Projects Communication and Accommodation Efforts

Projects Efforts to Improve Testing Uptake

Most (n=39/47; 83%) projects indicated agreement or strong agreement that their project is successful in increasing testing accessibility among their priority population(s) (Figure 9). More than half of the projects (n=10/15; 66.6%) indicated agreement or strong agreement that their project has been able to easily connect with the CDCC to request support in mitigating challenges (Figure 10). More than half of projects (n=10/15; 66.6%) indicated agreement or strong agreement that the CDCC has been responsive to their requests around procurement assistance, while 40% (n=6/15) of projects agreed that CDCC helped them resolve their procurement challenges (Figure 10).

Figure 9: RADx-UP Projects' Effort to Increase Testing Accessibility (n=47)

Figure 10: CDCC Support to the RADx-UP Projects

Implementation Successes: Impacts of Community-Based Partnerships and Community Outreach/Engagement Activities

Leveraging Multi-level Partnerships to Accomplish Projects' Implementation Goals

More than half (n=52/80; 65%) of projects reported that they collaborate with community-based organizations (CBOs) to increase participant access to project sites, health care, and/or social services; See **Figure 11**. Eleven projects described in detail how they leveraged existing or developed new partnerships with diverse organizations, government, and community stakeholders to address implementation barriers, address recruitment challenges, shore up staffing needs, and build trusted relationships within projects' target communities.

Figure 11. Collaborating with CBOs to Increase Access to Social and Health services.

"We worked with our partnering organizations and community stakeholders to identify any barriers that would impede the implementation. Partnering with established healthcare organizations and utilizing CHWs from the community, helped tailor the interventions to fit the needs of the individual communities."

"Our project partnerships enhanced testing capabilities in [State] and helped our clinical partners around the state to address barriers and support additional clinical staff to help support testing demands, improve testing processes at the clinical level, and allocate personal protective equipment and laboratory support when needed. We partnered with local county health departments and successfully provided testing to the rural areas with a high demand for testing."

Projects also formed or utilized existing collaborations with community advisory boards (CAB) (n=38/83; 46%) and community steering committees (CSC) (n=5/83; 6%); See **Figure 12**. Nine projects described in detail the specific roles and functions of CABs and CSCs within each of their projects. Projects consulted with already developed advisory boards (n=1 project) or developed CABs and community steering committees (CSCs) (n=5 projects). Some projects consulted with multiple CABs (n=3 projects) while others engaged with only one CAB or CSC (n=5 projects) monthly or quarterly to guide testing intervention delivery/recruitment strategies,

tailoring test strategies, promotional messaging and increasing reach within target communities, testing delivery logistics (best location, times and community events). The meetings also provided opportunities for bi-directional learning between academics (receive insights about communities) and community partners (learn about the latest COVID-19 science) (n=3 projects).

Figure 12. RADx-UP Projects Working with CABs or CSCs

"The Community Steering Committee (CSC) meetings serve as an opportunity for resource sharing and bi-directional learning, with community partners receiving the most up-to-date information on the pandemic, and academic and municipal partners receiving valuable insight about our study population, as well as feedback on project plans and materials."

Actively Engaging Community Partners in Project Planning and Implementation Activities

Most projects (n=48/51; 94%) reported actively collaborating with their community-based partners on their planning and implementation activities (See [Figure 13](#)). Also, projects (n=83) reported that their community-based partners contribute to ongoing project planning and implementation in multiple ways (See [Figure 14](#)). The most frequently cited community partner contributions included outreach, recruitment, and retention (n=71 projects); serving as a community liaison (n=67 projects); contributing to project study design (n=48 projects); helping interpret or validate project findings (n=46 projects); and helping to deliver project interventions and/or service components (n=46 projects). Many projects also reported that their community-based partners lead project implementation (n=22 projects), collected project data (n=37 projects), and use project findings to improve the quality of project's implementation delivery (n=36 projects) etc.

Figure 13. Number of Projects Collaborating with Community-Based Partners

Figure 14. Community-Based Partners' Contribution to Project Planning and Implementation Activities

Fifteen projects described in detail how they actively involved their community partners in planning and implementing their project activities such as in leadership and decision-making (n=3 projects), hiring and training CHW (n=2 projects), delivering or advising on outreach and recruitment campaigns (n=7 projects), directly participating in shaping intervention design (n= 8 projects), providing feedback on project plans (n=2 projects) and assisting with translating study evidence into digestible outputs that can be shared within communities (n=2 projects).

"We worked collaboratively with community partners throughout each phase of the study, from the development of the

research protocols, operations, messaging, and materials (Phase 1) to the execution of chain-referral and credible messenger recruitment strategies (Phase 2), to the evaluation of research outcomes and the sustainability of each strategy within the CBO (Phase 3)”

“[Community partners] coordinate with their Community Advisory Board to review and provide feedback on study recruitment materials, make recommendations to overcome recruitment barriers, and help with dissemination of findings back to the community.”

Building Community Relationships and Community Capacity for Research

Projects reported that they are using multiple approaches to build community capacity for research.

Building Community Trust. Addressing trust is the primary way that projects reported they are contributing to community capacity building by building trusting relationships with their community-based partner(s) and other community stakeholders (n=77/83; 93% projects), **Figure 15**.

Figure 15. RADx-UP Projects Research Capacity Building Activities

Three projects described in detail how they have built relationships and community trust by hiring and training CHWs directly from the local community that can relate to the target population.

“Our research design and recruitment strategies have allowed us to better understand motivators and barriers Black communities face when testing for COVID-19. By hiring staff from our priority population and taking the time to educate participants on their rights, we have been able to build substantial trust within this population.”

Community Leadership. More than half of projects also reported they are ensuring community-based partner(s) take on project leadership roles (n=46/83; 55% projects), **Figure 15**. Three projects described how they involved community partners in project leadership and decision-making (n= 3 projects).

"The partner organizations have been invited to be co-investigators and they are fully involved in the study and to target population."

"Co-locate testing, co-design intervention, hiring support/connection to qualified staff, the community partner has the final decision about the testing and vaccination program and lead those programs."

Research, Training, and Skill-building. Many projects responded that they provide or promote training opportunities to develop the research skills of community-based partners (n=28/83; 34% projects), **Figure 15**.

"We hired and trained eight Community Health Workers (CHWs), one CHW supervisor, recruited 10 resident navigators from across each development, and obtained referrals and completed enrollments into the intervention."

Responsive and culturally appropriate service delivery

Projects indicated that their collaborating service organizations show cultural responsiveness in multiple ways such as utilizing culturally diverse staff that reflect the cultures of service users (n=49/83; 59%); acknowledging historical trauma of underrepresented populations (n=41/83; 49%); service providers receive training in culturally responsive care (n=37/83; 44.6%); and literature available uses plain language (n=35/83; 42%); See **Figure 16**.

Also, projects (n=39/83; 47%) reported that they work with a priority population(s) that includes individuals who are non-English speaking, multilingual, and/or may experience communication challenges (e.g., Deaf and/or Hard of Hearing).

"The project also focused on providing specialized testing to communities of color. Culturally competent testers traveled to communities with higher proportions of African American residents. Community-based testing occurred in these communities where medical mistrust is still very present and provided direct access to COVID-19 testing."

How services provided by community based partners are responsive to the cultural and health beliefs and practices of projects priority populations? (n=83)

See Appendix C for "other" categories.

Figure 16. Cultural Responsiveness of Services Provided by Community-Based Partners

Community Partnership Impact beyond COVID-19: Addressing SDOH needs within communities.

Beyond delivering testing and vaccination interventions, project partnership collaborations (n=2 projects) helped address other social needs (cash assistance, food distribution, isolation hotel during COVID-19 infection) and connecting participants to other primary care needs.

"We collaborate with [name..] Center, a free clinic for immigrants where we support their COVID-19 hotline and bilingual navigators and help connect participants to primary care. We also partner with the Mayor's Office of Immigrant Affairs and the Health Department, and our bilingual RAs connect participants to cash assistance, food distribution, and isolation hotel if indicated."

Projects' Impacts and Sustainability

In addition to their community-engaged work to increase COVID-19 testing access in underserved communities, projects have impacted communities through community capacity building for research; providing economic, policy, and community and public health benefits; and improved pandemic preparedness. Survey results also indicate that many of the projects' community-engagement strategies and activities to increase communities' access to COVID-19 testing and other health and social services will continue after grant funding ends. **Figure 2.** highlights thematic areas that the projects impacted as indicated through survey responses.

Economic, Policy, and Community and Public Health Benefits.

Projects indicated their work had economic, policy, and community and public health benefits for their priority population(s). More than half of projects (56%) reported their activities provided economic benefits (direct or indirect) to underserved populations primarily through helping to reduce the monetary costs of tests (n=38/83; 46%), the time to complete tests (n=33/83; 40%), the time to receive test results (n=28/83; %) and improving transportation access (n=26/83; 31%) (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Ways Projects Reduced Financial Costs of Covid-19 Testing

One project indicated how important the provision of transportation or delivering tests to community participants was to its testing intervention:

"We were able to conduct the navigation intervention for most participants. Easy accessibility of COVID-19 testing was offered to all participants by providing bus tickets to those that come in-house and bringing of test kits to those participants that were unable to travel."

About a quarter (n=23/82;28%) of projects reported that they have engaged in policy-related activities; See **Figure 18**.

Of those projects, the most frequently reported activities were:

- Presentation of data or results to government agencies, decision-makers, or policymakers (n=15 projects)
- Development or contribution to policy brief or non-technical document that included project findings (n=11 projects).
- Participation in a government or policy advisory committee or board (n=9 projects).

Figure 18. Engagement in Policy-Related Activities

Some projects provided community and health benefits by helping to bolster the public health infrastructure with testing in underserved communities during the pandemic when public health resources were strained as exemplified by this project’s experience:

Pandemic Preparedness

More than half of the projects (n=59/82; 72%) responded to their positive impact on pandemic preparedness in underserved communities (**Figure 19**). Also, survey results indicated that most project COVID-19 testing activities (n=43/47; 91%) appear to be agile and replicable in the face of a future pandemic (**Figure 20**).

Figure 19. Level Of COVID-19 Pandemic Preparedness

Figure 20. Testing Agility for Future Pandemics

Sustainability

Thematic analysis indicated the presence of factors that may pose a challenge to the sustainability of projects' activities. Some projects indicated that they and/or their partners have experienced *funding challenges* that can reduce or halt the continuity of provided testing, health, and/or social services as reflected in this quote:

"We are referring out to community testing sites and those are drying up by the day due to reduced public health funding."

COVID-19 fatigue and reduced perception of COVID-19 severity may lead to a decline in community participation in projects' testing and/or vaccination programming as expressed by another project:

"We've recently noticed that the perceived severity of COVID-19 has diminished, which impacts overall engagement with participants. Some staff are testing less frequently. Instead of testing each week, some are now testing every other week or less."

Despite these challenges, survey findings overall indicated that project activities, including testing, community engagement and intervention strategies, and healthcare and social services for priority population (s) will be sustained in some capacity after close out.

Of projects that increased testing accessibility, about a quarter (n=13/47; 28%) indicated that testing will continue in some capacity. More than half of projects (n=57/82; 70%) indicated that their community engagement strategies will continue and almost a third (n=27/82; 33%) have secured or will seek additional funding to sustain other project activities and interventions. Additionally, some projects (n=39/57; 68%) indicated that priority populations will continue to have access to project-related healthcare and social services.

Projects' Implementation Challenges

COVID-19 testing supply, logistics, implementation protocols, and uptake challenges.

Some projects (n=15/47; 32%) reported that they experienced some challenges in procuring necessary testing supplies, **Figure 21** Eighteen projects described the challenges they faced procuring and implementing COVID-19 test protocols. Technical malfunctions, chain-supply bottlenecks, staffing challenges, changes to NIH testing guidelines, and difficulties restocking specific testing kit brands were some of the procurement and testing implementation challenges described. Some projects (n=9) also reported that participants had low motivation and low demand for testing. They described uptake challenges such as low attendance at walk-up clinics, minimal engagement in repeat testing, and testing fatigue because of the widespread availability of vaccination.

Changes to NIH guidelines

"The largest challenges our project faced were: 1) changes to the NIH testing guidelines in November 2021, which halted our testing plan. Then, a lengthy period of approval for a new testing plan ensued which prevented the project from resuming testing and resulted in us missing a large SARS-CoV-2 wave."

Low motivation and demand

"Completing testing with the population of focus was our biggest challenge. We contacted non-responders to give support for ordering and completing. Many complained about the handoff process to the testing partner and described several procedural barriers to completing testing."

"The challenge faced was the shift in testing desire with the release of the COVID-19 vaccine in early 2021. Many communities felt testing was no longer needed once a person received the vaccine."

Logistic and supply challenges

"[We experienced challenges] Procuring testing supplies, dealing with logistics of adding testing to clinical routine care."

Figure 21. Procurement and Testing Supply Challenge

Project administration challenges (staffing capacity, resources, space, IRB delays)

Projects (24/83; 31%) faced challenges in hiring and retaining staff [Figure 22], especially those with strong data collection and analytical skills (n=17/83; 20%), Figure 23. Fifteen projects described facing staffing capacity challenges. They experienced staffing shortages which affected the number of staff available to perform technical skills such as administering COVID-19 tests or performing data analysis [Figure 23]. Staffing resource constraints affected projects' ability to readily collect, analyze, and disseminate data as well as translate findings into user-focused, easily digestible products for community-centered dissemination including publishing in peer-reviewed journals. The time taken to get IRB approvals, especially for projects with intervention components (n=7 projects), and the shifting NIH testing requirements/guidelines (n=2 projects) also delayed some projects' implementation start-up.

Administrative Delays

"Administrative and regulatory delays have pushed the overall project timeline back by 2-3 months."

Staff Capacity

"Staffing, we currently do not have enough full-time staff to assist with on-site data collection/analysis. Students/volunteers are wonderful however we are in need of more full-time staff to help."

"Operations were difficult when we did not have enough staff or space to properly coordinate intake, surveys, and blood tests during large recruitment events."

Figure 22. Challenges in Hiring Qualified Staff

Figure 23. Skills Associated with Limited Staffing Capacity

Challenges Related to Recruitment, Enrollment, Retention, and Participant Engagement in Intervention Activities

Eighteen projects described their recruitment, enrollment, retention, and participant engagement challenges. They cited the following as reasons for experiencing low enrollment and retention:

- Waning interest in COVID-19,
- Test logistic issues,
- Staff availability and capacity,
- Inability to reach the target population because of language barriers and health literacy,
- Difficulties enrolling eligible participants that are not being engaged/interacting within their communities,
- Limited participant bandwidth and motivation challenges.

Other challenges experienced included difficulties following up with enrolled participants because they have limited interests in continued repeat COVID-9 testing.

"The biggest challenge is outreach with the population we serve. Many of the families are not engaged in the school community; parents generally work long hours. Health literacy is also a concern with this population. Another challenge is mixed messaging from politicians, school administration, district administration, and our health/research team. Therefore, we have had to make more efforts to gain the trust of the families in our school populations."

"Low engagement around repeat testing regimen (2x a week for 4 weeks -- total of 8 tests) was a challenge that the project faced. While successful in engaging participants to take an initial COVID-19 test, it was challenging to retain participants and have them return for follow-up test appointments."

Community-Specific Barriers to Intervention Delivery

Some projects (n = 6) experienced unique challenges because of their study settings or the needs of their target population. For example, coordinating with some Pacific Islander communities and migrant workers mostly engaged in hourly-type work presented a challenge due to their limited availability to participate in the projects. Migrant workers were also reluctant to talk about COVID-19 testing or vaccination because of the perception that testing positive may impact their work and livelihood. Language barriers impacted questionnaire completion time despite translation efforts. Also, some projects noted that there is a need for more able-centered planning and resources for providing testing and vaccination access to disabled and mentally challenged individuals.

"One challenge in rural West Virginia communities is always the weather. West Virginia has harsh winter road conditions that pose challenges for staff to report to the testing sites and participants to come for testing from their homes."

"Language barriers - we try to address this by translating documents and having multilingual team members but can still be a challenge."

Partnership Coordination and Community Capacity Challenges

Coordination: Five projects described challenges related to coordinating and engaging diverse stakeholders, getting buy-in and support from their partners, addressing data sharing and transfer roadblocks and dealing with spacing resource constraints by being flexible to the needs of their partnering health centers and adapting their implementation activities to partners' clinical workflows so as not to disrupt usual patient care.

"Some of the challenges we have faced thus far have been hesitancy of sharing sensitive, internal jail information as part of this project and identifying members of our implementation team."

"1. Lengthy negotiations on understanding Tribal Sovereignty on CDE's, data acquisition and sharing. 2. Harmonizing between multi-discipline and multi-team (EIT) external requests have been challenging (timewise)."

Capacity: Six projects described dealing with capacity constraints especially when it related to actively engaging with partners, CABs, CSCs, and other community-based organizations. Projects had to adapt their implementation protocols and plans to fit into the evolving capacities of the partners. Projects had to be flexible to accommodate community partners' bandwidth; they also had to collaborate with the communities to build up community workers' capacity for research.

"Shifting timelines and the capacity of community partners has been a challenge, so we have had to remain flexible with the implementation of our project"

"Training lay health workers to give educational sessions over Zoom. Making sure participants are comfortable and able to attend meetings over Zoom"

Data-related (capacity for data collection, analysis, and dissemination) Challenges

Projects experienced numerous challenges with data collection, analysis, and dissemination. Thirty-two projects described in detail their data-related challenges such as:

- Timely data collection and interpretation challenges (n = 4 projects)
- Limited resource and capacity for data collection and analysis (n = 15 projects)
- Complexities with common data elements (CDEs) (n = 10 projects)
- Data management and harmonization (n=3 projects)
- Dissemination Challenges (n = 4 projects)

For data collection, challenges cited include the rapid evolution of the pandemic and general COVID-19 fatigue creating barriers to completing data collection and disseminating timely and relevant data. Projects also experienced staffing shortages and time and analytical capacity constraints (i.e., few project staff have data science expertise) as well as difficulties administering the CDE survey to their participants (i.e., requires considerable time, effort, and knowledge to complete). For some other projects they had to deal with delays associated with data transfer, data harmonization and data management. Projects also needed help translating their findings into use-focused, easily digestible products for community-centered dissemination as well as publishing their findings on time in reputable journals.

Capacity for Data Collection and Analysis

"Data science capability - ability to extract/organize existing school district data given data security requirements and

given size of data, as actionable data requires immediate analysis/viewing by the research team and partnered districts"

Complexities with CDEs

"Amount of data - CDEs are extensive and require significant time and effort for participants to complete. Some opt not to complete the study for this reason"

Other External Environmental Factors Inhibiting Motivation/Interest to Test (n=11)

Environmental factors directly beyond the projects' locus of control affected testing implementation activities. Projects reported seeing COVID-19 testing fatigue (n=5) among their populations because of waning public interest in the pandemic (n=2), declining infection rates (n=1), and reduction in the perceived value of testing because of widespread availability of vaccination (n=3).

"We've recently noticed that the perceived severity for COVID 19 has diminished, which impacts overall engagement with participants. Some staff are testing less frequently. Instead of testing each week, some are now testing every other week or less"

"Another challenge faced was the shift in testing desire with the release of the COVID-19 vaccine in early 2021. Many communities felt testing was no longer needed once a person received the vaccine"

Conclusion

RADx-UP projects have achieved tremendous success in implementing their COVID-19 testing and vaccination activities and interventions.

Increasing access to and Uptake of COVID-19 Testing within Underserved Communities

- A significant proportion of projects (83%) reported an increase in testing accessibility among their priority populations.
- Projects described how culturally responsive strategies, such as hiring staff from the community, providing translation services, and accommodating language needs, crafting culturally appropriate messaging, and delivering interventions congruent with community values, allowed them to improve testing uptake within underserved communities.
- Tailoring testing interventions to community needs, offering at-home or school-based testing, providing tests at multiple locations, and offering incentives like transportation or financial support were reported as effective strategies for increased testing uptake.

Community Engagement and Collaboration with Multi-level Partners

- Over 65% of projects collaborated with CBOs and stakeholders. These collaborations proved instrumental in overcoming barriers to testing and building trusted relationships within communities.
- Community-based partners actively contributed to project planning and implementation, taking on roles ranging from outreach, recruitment, and retention to study design, data collection, and using findings to enhance implementation quality.
- CABs and CSCs played pivotal roles in guiding testing intervention strategies and facilitating bi-directional learning between academic and community partners.

Broader Impacts and Sustainability

- RADx-UP Projects have not only increased COVID-19 testing access but also positively impacted communities through capacity-building, economic benefits, policy influence, and improvements in public health pandemic preparedness.
- Over half of the projects reported reducing the monetary cost of testing, showcasing the economic benefits of the RADx-UP program.
- Beyond COVID-19 interventions, project collaborations addressed broader social needs like cash assistance, food distribution, and connecting participants to primary care services.
- Factors like COVID-19 fatigue and reduced perception of severity were suggested to decrease

community participation, posing challenges to the continuity of testing and vaccination programs.

- Despite these challenges, the overall findings indicate that projects are adaptable and resilient in the face of changing public needs, motivation, and requirements for COVID-19 testing and vaccination.

Summary of Findings

- Although RADx-UP Projects contributed significantly to developing community-led research collaboratives, we still need to understand the longer-term impact of community engagement strategies on improving health equity outcomes and explore ways to maintain community participation in testing and vaccination programs as public perceptions evolve.
- The RADx-UP projects have successfully implemented COVID-19 testing and vaccination interventions, leading to increased testing accessibility, community capacity-building, and public health preparedness.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Survey Section	Description of Data Collected by Survey Section
1)Project Resources	This section collects information on project staffing capacity including types and count of staff categories, and challenges to hiring staff with skills needed to implement project activities
2)Project Services	This section collects information on how projects address behavioral issues that may affect underserved populations’ access to or uptake of testing and vaccination such as through direct provision of tests and intervention studies. Data is also collected on the strengths and challenges to projects’ strategies to increase priority population testing (reach and effectiveness).
3)Partnerships and Community Engagement	This section collects information on projects’ community-based partnership(s), (including types of partners and collaboration to increase priority population's access to project sites, healthcare and/or service) s, community engagement, and cultural responsiveness to priority populations’ beliefs and practices
4)Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion	This section collects information on the support of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) within the project’s team and workplace
5)Language and Communication Access	This section collects information how projects accommodate the language and communication needs of diverse priority populations
6)Data Collection, Analysis, and Dissemination	This section collects information on project's data collection operations, analysis process, and plans for dissemination of findings, including challenges
7)Project Impact and Sustainability	This section collects information on project's impact, including on community capacity-building for research, policy and economic benefits, pandemic preparedness, and plans for sustainability.

Appendix B

Definitions, Summaries and Frequencies of Key Themes and Subthemes

Main Themes	Subthemes
Implementation Successes	
<p>Developing and Disseminating Community Outreach and Education Resources to improve recruitment as well as COVID-19 vaccination and testing (n=12 projects).</p> <p><i>Projects are using social media, text messages and project websites to recruit participants and reach testing targets. They also promoting COVID-19 testing and vaccination knowledge through community forums, interactive web-based data dissemination approaches and using community health workers to promotes awareness.</i></p>	<p>Outreach and recruitment resources through</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media and mobile messaging outreach (n=5 projects) • Web-based engagement (n=2 projects) <p>Health promotion and education resource (n=4 projects)</p>
<p>Increasing COVID-19 testing uptake through culturally responsive and tailored intervention strategies n=28 projects)</p> <p><i>Projects ensured that they used cultural-responsive strategies such as hiring staff directly from the community, crafting culturally appropriate messaging to motivate testing and delivering interventions congruent with community needs and values.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailoring intervention approach (n=10 projects) (providing incentives, transportation, at-home testing) • Increasing testing uptake through At-home testing (n=4 projects)

<p><i>Tailoring intervention strategies such as meeting respondents where they are, providing at-home or school-based testing, providing tests at multiple location, and providing transportation or other financial incentives to motivate people, increased COVID-19 testing uptake.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing testing through school-based programs (n=2 projects) • Increasing testing through multi-setting testing campaigns (n=3 projects) • Culturally responsive intervention design and outreach (community-events, hiring staff from community, providing translation services) n= 14 projects
<p>Leveraging multi-level partnerships to deliver testing intervention (n= 11 projects)</p> <p><i>Projects leveraged partnerships with diverse organizations, government, and community stakeholders to address implementation barriers, address recruitment challenges, shore up staffing needs to support testing demands and build trusted relationships within communities.</i></p>	
<p>Actively involving community partners in project planning, design, and implementation (n=15 projects).</p> <p><i>Projects actively collaboration with their community partners in planning program implementation activities such as hiring and training CHW, delivering or advising on outreach and recruitment campaigns, positively strengthening projects relation with their target communities, directly participating in shaping intervention design, providing feedback on project plans and assisting with translating study evidence into digestible outputs that can be shared within communities.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outreach and recruitment (n=7 projects) • Leadership and decision making (n=3 projects) • Hiring and training CHW staff (n=2 projects) • Building relationships with the community (n=3 projects) • Project planning, design, and intervention delivery (n=8 projects)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing feedback on study plans (n=2 projects) • Dissemination of findings (n=2 projects)
<p>Developing and consulting with community advisory boards or community committees (n = 9 projects)</p> <p><i>Projects consulted with already developed advisory boards (n=1) or developed CABs and community steering committees (CSCs) (n=5 projects). Some projects consulted with multiple CABs (n=3 projects) while others engaged with only one CAB or CSC (n=5 projects) monthly or quarterly to provide guidance on testing intervention delivery/recruitment strategies, tailoring test strategies, promotional messaging and increasing reach within target communities, testing delivery logistics (best location, times and community events). The meetings also provided opportunities for bi-directional learning between academic (receive insights about communities) and community partners (learn about latest COVID-19 science) (n=3 projects).</i></p>	<p>Purpose of meetings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intervention methods and delivery/logistics (n=3 projects) • Recruitment and outreach strategies (n=3 projects) • Tailoring strategies and messaging (n= 2 projects) • Disseminating findings and bi-directional learning (n=3 projects)
<p>Impacts beyond COVID-19 addressing SDOH needs within communities (n=2 projects)</p> <p><i>Beyond delivering testing and vaccination interventions, project partnership collaborations helped address other social needs (cash assistance, food distribution, isolation hotel during COVID-19 infection) and connecting participants to other primary care needs.</i></p>	
Implementation Challenges	
<p>Project administration challenges (staffing capacity, resources, space, IRB delays) (n=28 projects)</p> <p><i>Many projects experienced staffing shortages, limited capacity of staff available to administer tests or those with analytical or research dissemination skills as well as</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staffing capacity (n=15 projects) • Space/setting to deliver tests (n=1 project) • IRB approval -delays (n=7 projects)

<p><i>competing priorities and other demands affecting staff time. The time taken to get IRB approvals especially for projects with intervention component, and the shifting NIH testing requirements/guidelines significantly delayed implementation start-up.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative and regulatory requirements (CDCC, NIH): (n=2 projects)
<p>Recruitment, enrollment, and retention including participant engagement in intervention activities within target population challenges (n=18 projects)</p> <p><i>Projects experienced recruitment, enrollment, and retention challenges. They cited waning interest in COVID-19, test logistic issues, staff availability and capacity, inability to reach target population because of language barriers, health literacy, difficulties enrolling eligible participants that are not being engaged/interacting within their communities, limited participant bandwidth and motivation as reasons for experience low enrollment and retention challenges. Other challenges include difficulties following up with enrolled participants because they have limited interests in continued repeat COVID-9 testing.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruitment, enrollment, and response-rate challenges (n=9 projects) • Challenges following up with participants (n=3 projects) Reaching project’s target population (n=5 projects) • Fostering community engagement/interaction (n=2 projects)
<p>Partnership coordination Challenges (n=5 projects)</p> <p><i>Projects described challenges related to coordinating and engaging diverse stakeholders, getting buy-in and support from their partners, addressing data sharing and transfer roadblocks and dealing with spacing resource constraints by being flexible to the needs of their partnering health centers and adapting their implementation activities to partners’ clinical workflows so as not to disrupt usual patient care.</i></p>	<p>Gathering support from multiple stakeholders (n=1 project)</p> <p>Data sharing and transfer among partners (n= 2 projects)</p> <p>Managing resource utilization with partners (n= 2 projects)</p>
<p>Community Capacity Challenges (n= 6 projects)</p>	

<p><i>Project had to adapt their implementation protocols and plans to fit into the evolving capacities of the partners. Projects had to be flexible to accommodate Community Partners bandwidth, they also had to collaborate with the communities to build up community workers capacity for research.</i></p>	
<p>Community-specific barriers to intervention delivery (n=6 projects).</p> <p><i>Projects experienced unique challenges because of their study settings or the needs of their target population. For example, coordinating with some pacific islander communities and migrant workers mostly engaged in hourly-type work limited their availability to participate in the projects. Migrant workers were also reluctant to talk about COVID-19 testing or vaccination because they believe testing positive may impact on their work and livelihood. Language barriers impacted questionnaire completion time despite translation efforts. Also, some projected noted that there is need for more able-centered planning and resources for providing testing and vaccination access to disabled and mentally challenged individuals.</i></p>	
<p>COVID-19 testing supply, logistics, implementation protocols and uptake challenges (n=18 projects)</p> <p><i>Eighteen projects described the challenges they faced procuring and implementing COVID-19 test protocols. Technical malfunctions, chain-supply bottlenecks, staffing challenges, changes to NIH testing guidelines and difficulties restocking specific testing kit brands were some of the procurement and testing implementation challenges described. Projects also reported that participants had low motivation and low demand for testing. They described uptake challenges such as low attendance at walk-up clinics, minimal engagement in repeat testing, testing fatigue because of widespread availability of vaccination.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply and procurement related challenges (n= 6 projects) • Changing protocols and requirements (n= 3 projects) • Uptake challenges: Low motivation and demand (n=9 projects)

<p>Data-related (capacity for data collection, analysis, and dissemination) challenges (n = 32 projects)</p> <p><i>Projects experienced numerous challenges with data collection, analysis, and dissemination. For data collection, they cited the rapid evolution of the pandemic and general COVID-19 fatigue creating barriers to completing data collection and disseminating timely and relevant data. They also experienced staffing shortages and time and analytical capacity constraints (i.e., few project staff have data science expertise) as well as difficulties administering the CDE survey to their participants (requires considerable time, effort, and knowledge to complete). For some other projects they had to deal with delays associated with data transfer, data harmonization and data management. Projects also needed help translating their findings into use-focused, easily digestible products for community-centered dissemination as well as publishing their findings on time in reputable journals.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timely data collection and Interpretation Challenges (n = 4 projects) • Limited resource and capacity for data collection and analysis (n= 15 projects) • Complexities with CDE (n= 10 projects) • Technical complexity (Data harmonization and transfer) (n= 3 projects) • Data dissemination challenges (n= 4 projects)
<p>Environmental challenges (COVID-19 waves, pandemic changes, roll-out of vaccination, COVID-19 fatigue) inhibiting motivation/interest to test. N=11 projects</p> <p><i>Environmental factors directly beyond projects locus of control affected projects testing implementation activities. Projects reported seeing COVID-19 and testing fatigue among their populations because of waning public interest in the pandemic, declining infection rates and reduction in the perceived value of testing because of wide-spread availability of vaccination.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapidity of pandemic changes (n=2) • Declining infection rates (n=1) • Vaccination roll-out lead reduced the perceived need for testing (n= 3) • COVID-19 and testing fatigue (n=5) • Reduced Funding (n=1)

Frequency counts for each theme could be higher because we are reporting the numbers by projects and not by projects' comments.

APPENDIX C: Tables showing the definitions of “other categories”

Other (please specify)	# of projects
Figure 4. Underserved populations served by RADx-UP projects (n=120)	n = 8 projects
• All Adult Residents (18 years or older) of 12 counties	1
• Caregivers of high-risk children	1
• Community, Policy, and Institutional Stakeholders in Orange County, CA	1
• Had to have a diabetes diagnosis.	1
• Non-native Hawaiian / Pacific Islanders	1
• Communities with the greatest social vulnerability to COVID-19	1
• Uninsured	2
Figure 6. RADx-UP Role (n=83)	n = 6 projects
• Project Director	1
• Project Coordinator	1
• Research Staff	1
• Completing survey with three members of our core project team	1
• Data Manager	1
• Lead CRC	1
Figure 7. Project Interventions to Improve COVID-19 Testing	n = 16 projects
• At-Home testing	2
• Not a testing intervention project	5
• Conducted outreach at church communities and Public Housing; Participated at scheduled community gathering and activities.	2
• Text messaging, study website, web-based infographics and Zoom	3
• providing testing kits and multiple testing services (on-site and off-site)	4
Figure 14. Ways your Community-Based Partners(s) Contribute to Ongoing Project Planning and Implementation (n=83)	n=5 projects
• Church and Cultural groups of Pacific Islander communities have contributed to our ongoing planning and implementation.	1
• Community Advisory Board members continue collaborations and discussions regarding COVID-19 testing and vaccination.	1
• Partners have served as Key Informants in 100 interviews and have contributed over 400 survey responses to help us understand the experience of the priority population. Partners have provided process data (field notes,	1

audio recordings, IVR data) for content analysis. All efforts have informed our development of health communication materials.

- Program sustainment. 1
- They do not contribute; we just called the locations to ensure that they were administering the COVID-19 vaccine. 1

Figure 15. Which of the following ways does your project contribute to community capacity-building? (n=83) n = 4 projects

- Community-based partners are also training institutional partners on how to best work with the community. 1
- Maintains social relationships and builds political power in priority populations. 1
- The partner organizations have been invited to be co-investigators and they are fully involved in the study and to target population. 1
- We are unable to make general statements about the community partners because some may apply to some organization and not others. 1

Figure 18. How has your project engaged in policy activities? (n=83) n = 4 projects

- Community based partners are also training institutional partners how to best work with the community 1
- Maintains social relationships and build political power in priority population 1
- The partners organizations have been invited to be co-investigators and they are fully involved in the study and to target population. 1
- We are unable to make general statements about the community partners because some may apply to some organizations and not others. 1

Figure 17. Which of the following ways has your project helped to reduce the financial cost of COVID-19 testing for your priority population (s), either directly or indirectly? (n=83) n=7 projects

- We managed to distribute FREE kit tests to families in need. 1
- The CHCs received money for participation-- most used one or more of these strategies. 1
- Sent at-home test to participants' home for free. 1
- Provided free self-testing kits. 1
- Our clinics are not mobile, but we've established weekly testing clinics in the community. 1

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Familiarized the testing process for "hard-to-test" kids who can now possibly be tested at home or more easily at a standard clinic rather than needing doctor/specialty visits or alternative methods due to the inability to collect samples 	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By providing free at-home covid tests we have reduced monetary, time, and transportation costs. 	1
Figure 23. Skills that have been challenging to hire staff for	n = 10
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bilingual/bicultural staff 	2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hiring a security guard 	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic research techniques and considerations 	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academics who have experience with community-based research and community organizations who have experience with academia. 	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clinical trial coordination is a specialized skill and takes time to teach. Can be difficult to find outside AMCs 	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pacific Islanders (PI) in Hawaii are grossly underrepresented in college education. Finding qualified PI who have the expertise and skills in research work has been a huge challenge. 	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data science, including data extraction and storage of FIRPA/HIPAA protected school district dat 	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges to administratively Hire folks with a criminal legal system history (our target pop) 	1

